

School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) for Intermediate Level: Narratives of School Coordinators

Rosilyn P. Salupan

Abstract. This study examined the implementation and effects of the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) at the intermediate level by focusing on the perspectives of school coordinators in New Bataan, Davao de Oro. Using a descriptive-qualitative approach, the study involved 10 public school teachers who served as Grade 5 coordinators. Through semi-structured interviews, these participants shared their narrative experiences with their roles, the implementation program, and the outcomes they observed. The findings indicated that the coordinators played a crucial role in the success of the program; they ensured food safety, coordinated with various stakeholders, and prioritized the well-being of the learners. Additionally, the study revealed that coordinators adopted effective coping mechanisms, such as forming community partnerships, resourcefully using available materials, and maintaining a positive outlook despite challenges. Beyond meeting nutritional needs, the SBFP was perceived to have contributed to the holistic development, improved nutrition, increased attendance, enhanced classroom focus, and boosted overall engagement of the learners. The program also fostered stronger ties among the school, learners, and the wider community. Based on these narratives of school coordinators, it was recommended that the SBFP continue to receive support and be further improved, with additional resources directed towards coordinator training and community involvement. Regular monitoring and evaluation were also suggested to address ongoing challenges and ensure program quality. Hence, strengthening stakeholder collaboration was considered essential for sustaining the positive effects on both development and the school community of the learners. This study highlighted the vital role that dedicated coordinators played in the success of school-based programs.

KEY WORDS

1. School-Based Feeding Program
2. Intermediate Level
3. school coordinators

Date Received: April 18, 2026 — Date Reviewed: April 21, 2026 — Date Published: May 19, 2026

1. Introduction

The School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) for intermediate-level students plays a vital role in promoting both nutritional well-being and academic performance. However, narratives from school coordinators reveal a range of persistent challenges that hinder the program's full potential. Key issues include frequent disruptions in the supply chain, leading to inconsistent meal delivery; limited funding that restricts the variety and quantity of food provided; and logistical difficulties in distributing meals across multiple school sites. Additionally, many staff members lack adequate training and resources, which complicates effective program implemen-

tation. Coordinators also highlight that external socio-economic factors, such as ongoing food insecurity at home, further limit the SBFP's impact. Together, these obstacles undermine the program's effectiveness and its ability to support students' health and educational success.

Globally, as studied by Dukhi (2020) and Zerga et al. (2022), malnutrition, which occurs when children lack, have too much, or fail to properly use essential nutrients, can greatly hinder their brain development and behavior, impacting both cognitive and physical abilities. This issue often leads to poorer academic performance, with affected students experiencing learning difficulties, increased absenteeism, and overall lower achievement. Beyond academics, malnutrition also affects children's emotional, social, and physical growth, contributing to ongoing cycles of disadvantage and inequality.

Meanwhile, Flores (2023) notes that several elements influence how effective and sustainable the SBFP can be, including challenges in implementing the program successfully, which are linked to socio-economic, social, psychological, and demographic factors. (Rahmah et al., 2025), aiming to reduce malnutrition and boost educational achievement, the program is noted for its ambitious scope. However, the 2024 Global Survey of School Meal Programs shows that Indonesia remains one of 17 countries without a large-scale school feeding program, as the MBG initiative is still being developed.

In the Philippine context, Reyes (2025), particularly in the province of La Union, the Department of Education (DepEd) is scaling up its School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) to tackle malnutrition and boost the well-being and academic success of students in need. This initiative offers nutritious meals to public school learners, while also encouraging good nutrition and hygiene practices. In addition, (Webb et al., 2018), in Tandag City Division, malnutrition remained a critical public health issue, especially among school-aged children, exacerbating the

challenges faced by educators in delivering quality education.

Furthermore, Tatad, E.F. (2025), the Nutrition Medical and Nutrition Team of the Davao del Sur Division has observed that a significant number of elementary students remain severely wasted or malnourished in recent years, particularly following the pandemic. In response, the Local Government Unit of Davao del Sur, in partnership with the Schools Division Office, has collaborated to address malnutrition by continually improving the Division Feeding Program.

Moreover, Alcantara & Fronteras (2024) highlight that nutrition-focused feeding programs can enhance students. SBFP coordinators in New Bataan, particularly in the Davao de Oro division, are likely to identify concerns regarding funding, resource management, and stakeholder involvement. Challenges such as delayed budgets, inconsistent parental support, food quality issues, and student engagement are common. Coordinators often adapt through improvisation and advocate for better training and sustained support to improve program outcomes.

In the same vein, SBFPs are crucial for funding, resource management, and stakeholder support; however, a lack of these hinders these programs, while increased funding, adherence to policies, and community engagement strengthen them and are crucial to combating malnutrition and promoting equitable education. Continued commitment and collaboration are key to overcoming obstacles and ensuring all children receive nutritious meals to support their growth and learning.

In the local setting, in Davao de Oro, the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP), guided by RA 11037, delivers nutritious hot meals and milk to undernourished students. Likewise, in the districts of New Bataan, Davao de Oro, school coordinators from schools such as Taytayan, Pagsilaan, Andap, Cabinuangan, and

Katipunan Elementary have been actively implementing the SBFF to enhance student health and learning outcomes. These coordinators work closely with local barangay officials, parents, and teachers. A potential research gap in implementing the SBFF at the intermediate level is the limitations of its implementation. Studies focus on immediate nutritional outcomes; there is a lack of comprehensive data evaluating how sustained participation in the program influences students' academic achievements, attendance, and physical development over time.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this study was to examine the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) for intermediate-level students through the narratives of school coordinators within the New Bataan District. It aimed to capture their experiences and perspectives on the program's implementation and impact. A study by WHO (2024) defines health as complete physical, mental, and social well-being, not just the absence of illness. By doing so, the study sought to identify key successes and challenges that were encountered in promoting student well-being and academic performance.

A study by Deuna and Doncillo (2024) found that shifting the SBFP from pre-pandemic to post-pandemic operations brought significant challenges, particularly due to limited funding. Lara and Saracostti (2019) suggested that active parent collaboration could help address these issues. Sahagun (2022) emphasized that broad community involvement is essential for the program's long-term success and the well-being of the children. Hence, the successful and sustainable implementation of the SBFP relies on adequate funding and strong collaboration among parents and the wider community.

1.2. Research Questions—1. What are the narratives of experiences of School Coordinators in implementing the SBFP for Intermediate Learners?

2. How do school coordinators cope with the challenges in implementing the SBFP?

3. What educational insights are gained from the narratives of SBFP coordinators?

1.3. Significance and Scope—The results of this narrative of the coordinators of the school study were significant in the following:

Learners. Gained awareness of the benefits that school feeding programs offer for both their health and academic achievement. Proper nutrition, improved student performance, and regular access to nutritious meals can support learning. This understanding can motivate learners to take part in such initiatives.

Teachers. Provide practical knowledge about the importance of nutrition for effective learning. Insights can guide teachers in supporting needs and helping learners foster a more productive educational environment.

School coordinators. Received detailed feedback on the challenges and successes in implementing the feeding program. The narratives offered valuable strategies for managing day-to-day operations. The study emphasized the importance of teamwork and clear communication, and school coordinators can use these lessons to improve program delivery.

The Department of Education. Refine policies and provide better support for feeding programs and identify key areas where additional resources or training may be needed. Community involvement for program sustainability to enhance the overall effectiveness of school nutrition efforts.

This study specifically examined the School-Based Feeding Program for intermediate-level students by gathering and analyzing the narratives of school coordinators. It aimed to understand their firsthand experiences, challenges, and insights related to the implementation and effectiveness of the program within their respective schools.

The research was limited to the perspectives of school coordinators, excluding other stakeholders such as students, teachers, and parents. Additionally, the findings may not be general-

ized beyond the selected schools or different educational contexts, as the focus was confined to a particular level and set of participants.

1.4. Theoretical Lens—The study is grounded in two theoretical frameworks: ecological systems theory and new literacies. These frameworks were selected for their ability to offer insights into the connections between the home environment, literacy practices, and technology. Each framework offers a distinct perspective that guides the organization, interpretation, and analysis of the data collected in this research.

This study was anchored on the Social Learning Theory. The Social Learning Theory, proposed by Albert Bandura, emphasizes the role of observation, modeling, and social interactions in the learning process. It implies that people learn from others' activities and experiences, both directly and indirectly (MSEd, 2022). Also, the research was grounded in Albert, which emphasizes the importance of observation, imitation, and social interaction in the learning process. Learners in the SBFF can observe and model healthy attitudes toward nutrition by watching classmates and teachers advocate for balanced meals.

On the other hand, Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory, which emphasizes learning through observation, imitation, and social interaction. In the context of the SBFF, students develop an emphasis on basic physiological needs, such as healthy eating habits, by observing and modeling the behaviors of their teachers and peers who advocate for balanced meals. This theory highlights how social experiences reinforce positive behavior changes, such as adopting better eating practices within the school community.

Similarly, individuals acquire new behaviors and knowledge by observing others and engaging with their social environment, both through direct experiences and indirect influences. In the context of the SBF, students can

develop positive nutritional habits by observing their peers and teachers promoting balanced diets and healthy eating practices. Food is a fundamental biological requirement. According to Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1970), humans have a hierarchy of needs, beginning with basic necessities such as food and safety, then progressing to higher-level needs. Therefore, providing adequate nutrition is essential prior to encouraging children to become motivated to learn. Nutrients in food serve multiple vital functions, helping to maintain overall health and well-being.

School coordinators managing the Grade Five learners understand that adequate nutrition is fundamental to supporting students' physical growth and cognitive development. Drawing on nutrition theories such as Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, it recognizes that meeting students' physiological needs, such as providing balanced meals rich in essential vitamins and minerals, is crucial for enabling them to focus on learning and personal growth. Observations from our experience show that children who receive nutritious meals tend to be more attentive, engaged, and healthier, as posited by Abraham Maslow in his Hierarchy of Needs (Maslow, 1943). In human motivation theory, fundamental physiological needs, such as food, are satisfied before higher-level needs, such as learning and self-actualization. School feeding programs provide the basic needs of learners so that they may concentrate on their studies.

The SBFF addresses these essential needs, enabling learners to concentrate better and engage more fully in their education. By combining Maslow's focus on fundamental needs with Bandura's emphasis on social learning, the program not only ensures proper nutrition but also promotes positive attitudes toward nutrition through role modeling, as reflected in the experiences shared by school coordinators. The Intermediate-level SBFP narratives from school coordinators through experiences and insights.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the research methodology used to examine the School-Based Feeding Program for intermediate learners in New Bataan, Davao de Oro. It explains how narratives were collected from school coordinators involved in the program and outlines the design, participants, data collection procedures, and analytical techniques used to gain a comprehensive understanding of the coordinators' experiences.

2.1. Method Used—This study employed a descriptive-qualitative approach, using a narrative framework to examine and illustrate the experiences and challenges of school coordinators in implementing the SBFF for intermediate learners. This approach aimed to capture the experiences of the participants as they naturally unfolded, free from preconceived notions or biases.

Environmental triangulation was a methodological strategy that involved examining the phenomenon from multiple environmental contexts to ensure a comprehensive understanding of participants' experiences. In qualitative research, especially within a phenomenological framework, it enhances the credibility and richness of findings by capturing how different settings or environmental factors influence lived experiences.

As a researcher exploring the implementation of the SBFP. In Davao de Oro, the researcher employed environmental triangulation to deepen my understanding of how different environmental contexts influence coordinators' experiences and program outcomes. By gathering data from coordinators working in diverse settings, highland, upland, and urban schools, the researcher aimed to identify commonalities and differences in challenges, resource availability, and community engagement support. This approach allows me to verify whether environmental factors consistently impact program delivery and to ensure that my findings are robust across varied contexts. Through this process, the researcher gain nuanced insights into how the local environment influences the co-

ordinators' roles and the effectiveness of the SBFP, which can inform the development of tailored strategies for implementation in various settings.

Moreover, incorporating environmental triangulation into your phenomenological study ultimately enhances the depth and validity of your findings. It enables you to explore the intricate relationships between individuals and their environments, revealing how various contextual factors influence their experiences with the implementation. By examining multiple settings, stakeholder perspectives, and environmental changes, your research can produce a comprehensive, authentic portrayal of the coordinator. This multi-environmental approach aligns with the phenomenological emphasis on capturing the richness of subjective experiences within their natural, multifaceted contexts.

According to McLeod (2024), phenomenology, qualitative research is centered on exploring the significance of lived experiences from the individual's viewpoint. Rather than testing hypotheses or aiming to generalize results to a broader population, phenomenological studies seek to highlight particular experiences and to question normative or structural beliefs by uncovering participants' personal perceptions and subjective realities.

2.2. Research Participants and Sources of Data—The participants of this study consisted of ten (10) for IDI and 1 group for FDG among public elementary SBPF school coordinators within New Bataan, Davao de Oro, based on specific inclusion criteria. To ensure rich, relevant data, participants must have been actively

serving as school coordinators for intermediate grades. They should have at least five years of experience in this role at their respective schools. Participants must be actively teaching at the time of data collection. They may be male or female and are currently serving as teachers and coordinators, ensuring they possess both practical and leadership experience necessary to provide comprehensive insights into the program's implementation.

Moreover, these coordinators are integral stakeholders in the implementation and management of the SBFP, which aims to improve learners' nutritional status and engage them through interviews. This methodological approach was designed to gather rich, detailed qualitative data by capturing the narrative of experiences of coordinators' challenges, and insights on the delivery of implementation within the SBFP. Their firsthand accounts are expected to shed light on the practical realities, coping mechanisms, and innovative strategies used to implement the program across different school settings. By involving these school coordinators, the researcher aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the operational dynamics, successes, and obstacles encountered in delivering the SBFP, particularly as they pertain to supporting reading development among grade 5 learners. Conducting these discussions on virtual platforms ensures broader accessibility and convenience, enabling participants to share their perspectives in ways that foster honest and detailed responses.

This purposive sampling approach ensured that participants provided detailed narratives about the SBFP for intermediate students. By selecting coordinators from schools actively involved in the SBFP, the study gathered valuable insights and firsthand experiences regarding the program's implementation, outcomes, and challenges. As Adeoye (2023) cited, purposive sampling is a common non-probability method in qualitative research, where participants are in-

tentionally selected based on specific criteria.

The sources of data consisted of ten (10) IDIs and FDG with school coordinators from Taytayan, Pagsilaan, Andap, Cabinuangan, and Katipunan Elementary Schools. These schools have been actively implementing the SBFP to improve student health and learning outcomes. The selection of these schools was based on their ongoing participation and commitment to the SBFP. Narratives and insights from the coordinators provided valuable information on the effectiveness and challenges of the program in various school settings, and they discussed how they cope.

2.3. Research Instrument and Role of the Researcher—The primary research instrument was a semi-structured interview guide designed to collect detailed narratives from public elementary school coordinators in the Davao de Oro district. Likewise, instruments that capture rich, descriptive information rather than numerical data often play a central role in facilitating this process.

This flexible tool allowed participants, including field notes, and digital tools like audio and video recorders, to capture the narratives 4experiences of school coordinators in the SBFP for intermediate grades. Following Bhandari's (2020) guidance, the research incorporated individual interviews, focus group discussions, open-ended questions, and direct observations. Relevant documents and recorded materials were also analyzed to support the findings. These methods provided a comprehensive view of the coordinators' roles and the effectiveness of the feeding program in schools. Each interview lasted approximately 45–60 minutes and was conducted at a time and venue preferred by the participant (Sundler et al., 2021).

The interview guide covered three major dimensions: (1) narrative experiences in implementing SBFP programs, (2) coping strategies in dealing with disaster-related challenges, and (3) educational management insights in pro-

moting SBFP sustainability. Follow-up probing questions were used to deepen understanding and encourage elaboration. This structure supported the phenomenological nature of the research, emphasizing rich, descriptive, and contextually grounded data (Roberts et al., 2022).

Before actual data collection, the instrument was validated by three experts: a specialist in qualitative research, an expert in SBFP school coordinators, and a professional in school leadership, who reviewed the instrument for relevance and clarity before the start of data collection. A teacher from a school not involved in the study participated in a pilot interview to further improve the tool by evaluating the questions' flow and cultural appropriateness. The accuracy and consistency of data collection were ensured by this validation process (Fusch et al., 2021).

In this descriptive-qualitative study, the researcher took on the responsibilities of interviewer, transcriber, and verifier. The primary goal was to collect reliable and shared insights into the narrative experiences, coping strategies, and challenges that school coordinators encountered while implementing the SBFP for grade 5 students. During the interviews, the researcher deliberately set aside my own perspectives to uphold the credibility of the research. I facilitated open-ended discussions and asked follow-up questions to gain a deeper understanding of participants' experiences.

The researcher transcribed and ensured that the transcripts accurately captured the participants' responses and used coded identifiers to maintain confidentiality. To further strengthen the study's trustworthiness, the researcher returned the transcripts to participants for review, allowing them to verify and confirm the accuracy of their statements. This process helped ensure that the collected data authentically represented the coordinators' perspectives.

2.4. Sampling and Procedure—This study used purposive sampling to select 10 for IDI and 1 group for FDG among public elementary

SBFP school coordinators within New Bataan, Davao de Oro. Participants came from Taytayan, Pagsilaan, Andap, Cabinuangan, and Katipunan Elementary Schools. Inclusion criteria required at least three years of teaching experience, active participation in feeding program activities, and completion of SBFP-related training with documented outputs such as evacuation plans and safety protocols. This method ensured the selection of information-rich participants with direct experience in SBFP implementation. As emphasized by Campbell et al. (2020), purposive sampling is appropriate in qualitative research for identifying participants who can provide deep, relevant insights into the phenomenon under study.

The data collection process primarily involved in-depth, semi-structured interviews supported by document analysis of school SBFP coordinators' plans, training certificates, and activity outputs. It was primarily conducted through IDI and FGD, complemented by observations and document analysis. These qualitative methods allowed for a thorough exploration of the lived experiences, perspectives, and challenges faced by school coordinators in implementing the SBFP within the New Bataan District. The chosen instruments provided flexibility for participants to express their thoughts openly, enabling the researcher to gather rich, descriptive data relevant to the research objectives.

Participants were purposefully selected based on predefined criteria to ensure that key informants with direct experience and involvement in the SBFP were included. Before data collection, the aims and procedures of the study were clearly explained to all participants, and informed consent was obtained to ensure ethical compliance. The researcher took additional care to uphold health and safety protocols throughout the process, including the use of face masks, physical distancing, and sanitizing materials, particularly in light of ongoing public health considerations.

All interviews and discussions were audio-recorded with the participants' explicit permission, ensuring the accuracy and integrity of the data. These recordings were then transcribed verbatim for detailed analysis, with both digital and hard copies stored securely to maintain participant confidentiality and prevent data loss. The use of open-ended interview guides and probing questions facilitated candid, comprehensive responses, providing a nuanced understanding of the coordinators' experiences and insights into the SBFP's implementation.

2.5. Data Analysis—The study employed Braun and Clarke's six-phase Thematic Analysis with De Farias et al.'s (2020) framework of similarity and levels of thematic complexity to enhance the depth and rigor of qualitative data interpretation. This combined approach enabled systematic coding and theme development, while also considering the degrees of thematic similarity and the hierarchical organization of themes, ranging from basic patterns to more abstract and complex themes. The synergy between these methods facilitated a nuanced understanding of the data, ensuring that themes were not only identified through iterative coding but also examined for their interconnectedness and levels of abstraction. This approach provided a systematic and flexible structure for identifying, organizing, and interpreting patterns across qualitative data.

The six phases included: (1) familiarization with the data, (2) generating initial codes, (3) searching for themes, (4) reviewing themes, (5) defining and naming themes, and (6) producing the report. Immersion in the data enabled the researcher to develop a holistic understanding of the participants' narrative experiences in implementing SBFP initiatives within their schools (Castleberry & Nolen, 2022).

First, the researcher familiarized themselves with the data by thoroughly reading the transcripts. They then generated codes by labeling meaningful segments, which were grouped to

identify potential themes. These themes were reviewed against the entire dataset for consistency and relevance. After refining and defining each theme, the researcher wrote the analysis and compiled the report. De Farias et al. (2020) enhanced this process by providing a structured approach that improved the consistency and development of codes and themes.

2.6. Ethical Considerations and Trustworthiness—The researcher is committed to upholding the highest ethical standards and ensuring the rights and dignity of all participants by avoiding exploitation and prioritizing their well-being. Before the study, the researcher secured official permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao de Oro and school principals, and obtained written consent from parents or guardians through signed assent forms, ensuring voluntary participation. This approach reflects a dedication to conducting ethical research that respects local contexts, promotes transparency, and safeguards stakeholders' interests.

Social Value. The researcher contributes to societal progress in New Bataan, Davao de Oro, by exploring the experiences of school coordinators implementing the SBFP for intermediate learners. The study seeks to highlight challenges faced by educators, providing insights to policymakers and educational authorities to develop more effective, sustainable strategies that support children's health and academic success. Ultimately, the research aspires to foster educational development and positively impact the community.

Informed Consent. Recognizing the importance of participant autonomy. The researcher provided each participant from New Bataan with comprehensive information about the purpose, procedures, and implications of the study. Participants signed consent forms voluntarily, affirming their understanding and willingness to contribute. Before data collection, consent was secured from all participants, with clear expla-

nations of confidentiality, the voluntary nature of participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. The researcher personally visited schools to ensure participants fully understood and consented freely (Tracy, 2022; Gentles et al., 2021).

Vulnerability of Participants. Given the professional background of the participants, experienced teachers in public elementary schools prioritized their comfort and understanding throughout the research. To address potential vulnerabilities, clear communication was maintained, and contact details were provided for questions or concerns, ensuring ongoing dialogue and ethical consideration.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. Participation was entirely voluntary, with assurances that withdrawal at any stage would incur no penalties. The research team provided contact information for support, and questionnaires were administered in secure, comfortable environments at convenient times to minimize risks. Responses were kept confidential through pseudonyms, safeguarding identities and prioritizing well-being. Participants could withdraw at any time without repercussions, trusting in the ethical conduct of the study.

Trustworthiness is the key element that determines the rigor of qualitative research (Amankwaa, 2016; Eryilmaz, 2022). A fundamental idea related to the trustworthiness of findings and interpretations is often discussed in the study. Although it shares similarities with validity and reliability found in quantitative re-

search, it uses distinct terminology tailored to the specific nature of qualitative methods. The assessment of this trustworthiness is typically based on four key criteria: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

Credibility. The researcher conducted in-depth interviews (IDIs) with ten school coordinators and focus group discussions (FGDs) from the New Bataan District in Davao de Oro, focusing on their experiences with implementing the SBFP for Intermediate Grades. Emphasis was placed on allowing participants sufficient time to share their insights, challenges, and perspectives. Throughout the interviews, the researcher also observed responses and non-verbal cues to gain a deeper understanding of their viewpoints and capture nuances beyond verbal expressions.

Transferability. The researcher aimed to ensure that the findings could be relevant and applicable beyond the immediate context. While qualitative research limits broad generalizations, a purposive sampling approach was employed to select participants that maximized the relevance and depth of the data within the specific setting. This approach facilitates consideration of how these insights might relate to or be adapted for similar environments.

Dependability. The researcher documented all procedures and methodologies in detail, providing transparency about data collection and analysis processes. This thorough documentation allows future researchers to replicate the study if desired, thereby establishing consistency and reliability in the research process.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents and discusses the findings of the study, addressing the research questions by presenting and analyzing responses gathered from the participants' narratives. Using a phenomenological approach, the study explored school coordinators' viewpoints regarding their experiences, coping strategies, and insights in implementing the School-Based Feeding Program at the intermediate level.

3.1. *Narratives of Experiences in Implementing the SBFP—implementing the SBFP for Intermediate Learners*

The narratives of school coordinators in implementing the SBFP for intermediate learners shed light on the various challenges and successes they face in promoting student health and academic progress. This will help to ensure that food safety and managing procurement, these coordinators work closely with different stakeholders to deliver nutritious meals and foster a supportive environment. Their lived experiences reveal the importance of effective teamwork, resource allocation, and community involvement in sustaining the program's goals. Exploring their firsthand accounts helps to better understand the practical aspects of running the SBFP and highlights areas where continued effort and innovation are needed to maximize its positive impact on learners.

According to Solania and Cubillas (2020), effective implementation of the SBFP hinges on collaborative engagement and strong partnerships among stakeholders. Furthermore, the results revealed a strong relationship between teachers' SBF knowledge of SBFP and the extent of their program implementation. In other words, the teachers' knowledge of the SBFP greatly helps them in the implementation of the school feeding program. Also, the coordinators have ensured that program beneficiaries are aware of health and nutrition. According to Robertson (2021), education about nutrition during the early developmental years, especially in preschool, significantly shapes an individual's lifelong health.

The implementation of the feeding program has significantly enhanced food safety practices and strengthened procurement processes, largely due to targeted training and stricter safety checks following health incidents. However, maintaining cleanliness during busy times and ensuring reliable suppliers remain are ongoing challenges. Regular stakeholder

meetings and formal agreements have bolstered teamwork and partnership among collaborators, though scheduling conflicts occasionally disrupt coordination.

Overall, the program has contributed to notable improvements in student health and well-being, with children exhibiting greater focus, energy, and attentiveness. Prioritizing nutritious meals, even amid budget constraints, has been essential, and strong parental involvement further supports success. These collective efforts have led to better academic performance, increased student morale, improved attendance, and reduced hunger, highlighting the positive and wide-ranging impact of the feeding initiative.

The findings of the study reveal that the Philippines' SBFP provides hot meals and milk to undernourished learners, aiming for 175 meal days and 120 milk days by 2025. It enforces strict procurement (RA 11321) and food safety protocols, including local sourcing, training, and monitoring.

Further, Demerin (2023), a well-organized feeding program, supplies students with necessary staple foods and adequate nutrition. However, dealing with malnutrition leads to escalated healthcare expenses, reduced productivity, and hindered economic advancement, perpetuating the cycle of poor health and poverty (Dukhi, 2020). The critical phase to address malnutrition is within the initial 1000 days of life, offering a strategic opportunity for implementing interventions aimed at enhancing child growth and development.

Additionally, in the study of Claros et al. (2024), beneficiaries often express dissatisfaction with the nutritional quality of distributed food, highlighting the need for a balanced diet. Thus, this study aimed to delve into teachers' knowledge and practices within the SBFP and how these influence pupils' academic achievements. The researchers believed that examining educators' impact on program success would

provide actionable insights for policymakers and school administrators to enhance educational outcomes through robust feeding initiatives. Indeed, it is apparent from the partici-

pants' responses that the school coordinators highlighted that SBFP find it difficult to provide assessments and feedback:

The narratives show that school coordinators perceived the SBFP as a program that extended beyond feeding. It involved food safety, procurement, collaboration, learner well-being, and academic improvement. Their accounts emphasized that effective implementation depends on training, clear coordination with stakeholders, parental support, and careful monitoring of learners' health and participation.

3.2. Coping Strategies in Implementing the SBFP—of the School Coordinators

The coping challenges used by school coordinators significantly shape their perceptions of challenges in implementing the SBFP. Coordinators who adopt positive strategies and efficient time-management practices, such as developing detailed schedules for meal preparation and distribution, are more likely to see issues like limited food supplies or staff shortages as manageable rather than overwhelming. Likewise, those who build strong relationships with local community leaders and parents, and regularly engage parent volunteers or work with local suppliers, tend to view issues such as parental non-compliance or resource shortages as less problematic.

Additionally, flexible leadership approaches, like adjusting meal menus based on available ingredients or reallocating tasks among staff, help mitigate workload burdens and logistical hurdles. Conversely, coordinators with poor coping strategies, such as disorganized schedules or weak community engagement, may perceive resource scarcity, parental non-cooperation, and heavy workloads as overwhelming obstacles. These observations underscore the importance of providing better stakeholder support, including training in time management, community

engagement, and resource planning, and of ensuring adequate resource allocation to enhance the overall effectiveness of the SBFP.

Coping strategies for school coordinators who struggle to manage the SBFP while also fulfilling their teaching responsibilities. Although the program is generally effective, challenges such as limited funding, logistical issues, and insufficient support from others frequently hinder its smooth implementation. A study by Bilbar (2020) found that the School-Based Feeding Program's physical facilities were highly effective, particularly in terms of cleanliness, organized feeding centers, access to clean water, proper storage, and efficient waste management systems.

The first theme, Positive Strategies, centers on how school coordinators leverage their strengths and recognize positive aspects within their roles. They break down larger goals into smaller, achievable tasks and cultivate resilience and adaptability when facing challenges. By building supportive relationships within their school community, they are better able to navigate difficulties, appreciate progress, and encourage a constructive and solution-focused environment. The participants shared their experiences, stating:

These narratives reflect that having a well-organized plan and strong relationships with colleagues allows me to quickly coordinate adjustments and ensure classes continue smoothly.

Oo, isip usa ka magtutudlo sa grade 5, ang pagtukod og maayong relasyon sa mga estudyante makatabang sa pagsulbad sa mga panagbangi nga dali ug makamugna og usa ka positibo nga palibot sa lawak-klasehanan.”

The second theme, Demonstrating Adap-

Table 1
Narratives of Experiences of School Coordinators in Implementing the SBFP for Intermediate Learners

Emergent Themes	Core Ideas	Significant Statements
Food Safety & Procurement	Improved food safety training Stricter safety health checks Prioritizing Hygiene	"Ang mga tigdumala sa pagkaon karon nagsunod sa husto nga mga protocol sa kaluwasan pagkahuman sa pagbansay, nga nagpakunhod sa mga peligro sa kontaminasyon."(IDI, P1). ("Food handlers now follow proper safety protocols after training, which reduces contamination risks." "Nagpahigayon og adlaw-adlaw nga pagsusi ug gipasiugda ang paghugas sa kamot aron masiguro ang kaluwasan sa pagkaon."(FDG 2) ("Conduct daily checks and emphasize handwashing to ensure food safety.")"
Stakeholder Collaboration	Regular stakeholder meetings Scheduling issues can disrupt coordination. Boost teamwork.	"Isip school coordinator, kinahanglan adunay regular nga miting uban sa mga stakeholders aron mapalambo ang pagpatuman sa programa kada quarter."(IDI, P5) ("As school coordinator, there should be a regular meeting with stakeholders to improve program implementation per quarter." "Sa among eskuylahan, ang usa ka pormal nga kasabutan sa mga hingtungdan magpatin-aw sa mga tahas ug mapalambo ang kolaborasyon" ("In our school, a formal agreement with the stakeholders would clarify roles and boost collaboration.") (IDI, P8). "Kami nagsilbi nga link tali sa mga stakeholder ug mga estudyante." (FDG 6) ("We serve as the link between stakeholders and students.")"
Student Health and Wellbeing	Focused and energetic. Improved Health and attentiveness Parental Role in Nutrition	"Mas pokus ug abtik ang mga estudyante sukad nagsugod ang feeding program, labi na kadtong gikan sa mga pamilyang ubos ang kita."(IDI, P4). ("Students are more focused and energetic since the feeding program began, especially those from low-income families.") "Ang kahimsog ug pagkaminagdanon sa bata miuswag pag-ayo salamat sa programa."(IDI, P5) ("The child's health and attentiveness have improved noticeably thanks to the program.") "Ang suporta sa ginikanan hinungdanon alang sa pagdasig sa mga bata nga makabenepisyo sa hingpit gikan sa programa." (FDG 2) ("Parental support is crucial for encouraging children to benefit fully from the program.)"
Academic Improvement	Improved academic performance and energy. Higher morale and eagerness to learn. Nutritious meals improve attendance and achievement.	"Isip school coordinator, akong naobserbahan ang mas maayo nga academic performance ug dugang nga lebel sa enerhiya sa mga estudyante."(IDI, P2) ("As school coordinator, I have observed better academic performance and increased energy levels among students.") "Nagpataas sa moral ug pagtamod sa kaugalingon. Ang mga estudyante naghinamhinam nga makakat-on."(IDI, P8) "Boosts morale and self-esteem. Students eager to learn." "Kini makatabang sa mga estudyante sa pagbuntog sa kagutom kasakit. Improved academic achievement."(FDG 1) "It helps students overcome hunger pangs. Improved academic achievement."

tive Leadership, means staying positive during change, adjusting plans as needed, listening to different ideas, encouraging others to get involved, and using feedback to keep improving. Flexible leaders adopt adaptable strategies such as sourcing food locally, creatively engaging parents, barangay, and leveraging LGU support to turn challenges faced by the SBFP, such as budget delays or low participation, into opportunities for innovation and collaboration.

The findings indicate that coordinators coped with implementation challenges by using positive strategies, adaptive leadership, and effective time management. These coping mechanisms helped them handle delayed budgets, procurement difficulties, competing teaching responsibilities, and coordination concerns while sustaining the implementation of the feeding program.

3.3. Educational Insights from the Narratives of SBFP Coordinators—The effectiveness of the program in improving academic performance lies in fostering a love of work, flexibility, and strong relationships. These reflections highlight the crucial role of collaboration among key stakeholders, including parents, school feeding coordinators in New Bataan, Davao de Oro, and the DepEd, in driving success. Integrating feeding initiatives with broader health education is a vital strategy for enhancing positive outcomes and promoting holistic development.

Furthermore, school coordinators frequently share inspiring personal stories of overcoming resource limitations, which foster stronger community engagement and underline the importance of resilience and creativity in program delivery. Witnessing remarkable improvements in children’s health and well-being further reinforces the value of dedication, strategic partnerships, and adaptive leadership. These insights demonstrate that sustained success relies on a collective effort, innovative strategies, and

This shift in perspective transforms setbacks into community-driven successes, ultimately enhancing nutrition and attendance. Through proactive measures such as ongoing monitoring and strengthening partnerships, these leaders turn negative perceptions, such as limited parental involvement or resource shortages, into calls for greater stakeholder commitment and systemic improvements.

a shared commitment to nurturing children’s growth and resilience.

As cited by Sadag (2025), increased funding flexibility, daily milk supplementation, dual SBFP coordinators, integration of Barangay Health Workers for monitoring, and improved community engagement through LGU-partnered resolutions are all suggested by the study as ways to improve program effectiveness. These enhancements are necessary to maintain and expand the beneficial impacts of the SBFP on long-term development outcomes, educational participation, and child health.

According to Table 3, SBFP coordinators report that shared meals improve nutrition, promote healthy habits, and reduce stress. These activities also strengthen community relationships, highlighting the role of social and emotional factors in overall well-being.

The findings of the study reveal that SBFP improves students’ nutrition and health by providing essential vitamins, fiber, and support for digestion, heart health, and overall well-being. These benefits are achieved through active community involvement, resource sharing, continuous advocacy, greater student participation, and strong partnerships. The program also strengthens school relationships by encouraging open dialogue, teamwork, shared accountability, and trust. In summary, SBFP boosts both student health and school-community collaboration. The first theme, Nutritional and Health

Table 2
The Coping Strategies in Implementing the SBFP of the School Coordinators

Emergent Themes	Core Ideas	Significant Statements
Positive Strategies	Using strengths, acknowledging and appreciating Breaking goals into manageable steps Positivity and flexibility boost collaboration.	"Alang kanako, ang paggamit sa mga tigplano nakatabang kanako nga magpabilin nga organisado. Nagtukod ako og relasyon sa mga ginikanan." (IDI, P2). ("For me, using planners helps me stay organized. I build rapport with parents.") "Oo, isip usa ka makakita sa grade 5, makita ang maayong relasyon sa mga estudyante makatabang sa pagsulbad sa mga panagbangi nga dali ug makamugna og usa ka positibo." (IDI, P9). ("Yes, as a teacher in grade 5, building good rapport with students helps resolve conflicts easily and creates a positive.") "Gigamit ang positibo nga mga estratehiya pinaagi sa pagdasig sa mga estudyante ug pagpauswag sa pagtinabangay." (FDG, P7) ("Use positive strategies by motivating students and fostering teamwork.") (
Demonstrate Adaptable Leadership	Embrace change with a positive mindset Adapt plans by seeking diverse input. Empower leads and learn from feedback for continuous growth.	"Kung nalangan ang budget sa among eskwelahan, nagkuha ko og pagkaon sa canteen ug nakig-alayon sa mga ginikanan pinaagi sa PTA meetings."(IDI, P1). ("If our school's budget was delayed, I sourced food in the canteen and engaged parents through PTA meetings.") "Sa pag-atubang sa ubos nga pag-apil sa ginikanan, isip usa ka magtutudlo sa grade 5, nagpahigayon ako og mga interactive workshop." (IDI, P2). ("Facing low parental involvement, as a grade 5 teacher, I held interactive workshops.") "Ang kakulang sa kahinguhaan nagdala kanamo sa pakigtambayayong sa barangay, ngadto sa mga oportunidad alang sa mas lig-on nga relasyon sa komunidad." (IDI, P4). ("Resource shortages led us to partner with the barangay for stronger community ties.") "Nag-organisar ko og flexible nga mga kalihokan. Nakigtambayayong ko sa (SBFP) coordinators ug intermediate nga mga magtutudlo." (IDI, P5) ("I organized flexible activities. I worked with the (SBFP) coordinators and intermediate teachers. "Nakigtambayayong ko sa barangay aron makahimo og shared delivery...
Effective Time Management	Set clear priorities and plan tasks with schedules. Set deadlines and delegate tasks. Reviewed and adjust the plans.	"Ang saktong pagplano ug delegasyon makatabang nako sa paghatag sa akong oras sa gawas sa paagi nga hapsay nga dili makaapekto sa akong uban nga mga responsibilidad."(IDI, P4). ("Proper planning and delegation help me manage run smoothly without affecting my other responsibilities.") "Ang nagpadayon nga pagbansay naghatag kanamo og mga estratehiya aron mas maayo nga madumala ang mga hagit sa logistik ug mapadako ang among oras." (IDI, P9). ("Ongoing training provides us with strategies to better handle the logistical challenges and maximize our time.") "Ang pagbaton og usa ka structured timetable nagsiguro nga ang pag-andam sa pagkaon, pag-apod-apod, ug paglimpyo gihimo sa tukmang oras." (FDG, P1). ("Having a structured timetable ensures that meal preparation, distribution, and cleanup are done on time.")"

Benefits, School-based feeding initiatives serve as vital safety measures, effectively reducing malnutrition, such as wasting and stunting, and boosting students' concentration, energy, and participation in learning. Reports indicate positive changes in BMI, lower rates of absence, and healthier eating behaviors among students.

A study by Assefa (2026). SBFP notably enhances children's nutritional health and fosters greater participation and academic success, with a particular benefit for girls and underrepresented groups. Additionally, SBFPs promote local economic growth by purchasing food from nearby farmers, thereby strengthening community resilience. As reflected in the narratives:

These statements suggest that the SBFP en-

hanced students' nutrition, leading to better growth and stronger immune systems, as seen in increased height and weight among beneficiaries and fewer reported cases of common illnesses.

Moreover, the (World Food Programme 2020) states that, under DepEd Order No. 031, series of 2021, those responsible for implementing the SBFP must consistently comply with food safety standards to ensure beneficiaries receive nutritious, safe meals. includes access to safe water, handwashing stations, and a clean, well-maintained environment, all of which support school feeding programs that improve attendance, enrollment, academic performance, and student health.

Table 3
Educational Insights Gained from the Narratives of SBFP Coordinators

Emergent Themes	Core Ideas	Significant Statements
Nutritional and Health Benefits	Boosts vitamins, fiber, digestion, and supports disease prevention. Aids muscle repair, prevents overeating, and promotes well-being.	"Ang pagkaon sa lainlaing prutas ug utanon naghatag sa imong lawas sa hinungdanon nga mga bitamina ug fiber sa pagkaon, nga nagpalig-on sa imong immune system." (IDI, P1) ("Eating a variety of fruits and vegetables provides your body with essential vitamins and dietary fiber, which strengthen your immune system.") "Isip usa ka school coordinator, ako nagtuo nga ang SBFF adunay importante nga papel sa pagsulbad sa kagutom ug malnutrisyon sa atong mga estudyante." (IDI, P7) ("As a school coordinator, I believe the SBFF plays a vital role in addressing hunger and malnutrition among our students.") "Pinaagi sa pagpraktis sa mahunahunaon nga pagkaon, maminaw ko sa mga timailhan sa kagutom sa akong lawas, mohimo og mas himsog nga mga pagpili sa pagkaon." (FDG, P1) ("By practicing mindful eating, I listen to my body's hunger cues, make healthier food.")
Community Support	Promote collaborative engagement and resources. mobilization. Sustained Awareness and Advocacy Builds trust to enhance student participation.	"Nakigtambayayong ko pag-ayo sa mga ginikanan ug magtutudlo aron masiguro nga hapsay ang dagan sa SBFP." (IDI, P2) ("I worked closely with parents and teachers to ensure the SBFP ran smoothly.") "Nakita nako kung giunsa ang komunidad naghiusa aron maghatag dugang nga pagkaon ug suporta alang sa programa." (IDI, P5) ("I saw how the community came together to provide extra food and support for the program.") "Mitabang ko sa pagpataas sa kahibalo bahin sa SBFP, nga nagdasig sa daghang mga tawo sa pagsuporta sa among mga paningkamot." (IDI, P7) ("I helped raise awareness about SBFP, which encouraged more people to support our efforts.")
Build Strong Relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Communication • Shared Responsibility • Trust and Transparency 	"Ako dayag nga nakigsulti sa mga ginikanan ug kawani, nga nakapasayon sa pag-coordinate sa SBFP." (IDI, P3) ("I openly communicated with parents and staff, which made coordinating the SBFP much easier.") "Gibati nako ang usa ka lig-on nga pagbati sa gipaambit nga responsibilidad samtang ang tanan nakatampo sa kaayohan sa estudyante." (IDI,P10) ("I felt a strong sense of shared responsibility as everyone contributed to student welfare.") "Ang pagka-transparent sa among mga proseso nakatabang sa pagtukod og pagsalig tali sa eskwelahan ug sa komunidad." (IDI, P7) ("Being transparent in our processes helped build trust between the school and the community.")

4. Summary, Conclusions, and Recommendations

This chapter provides a summary of the key findings of the study, discusses the implications of the results, and offers recommendations based on the analysis. The research focused on examining the lived experiences of school coordinators, their coping mechanisms, and their perspectives on the challenges faced during the implementation of the SBFP, drawing insights from their narratives. Twelve public school teachers from New Bataan, Davao de Oro, were purposively selected for their dual roles in both teaching and administrative functions, such as serving as department heads, coordinators, or committee leaders. Preference was given to those with at least three years of experience in these capacities to ensure the collection of relevant and practical insights. A descriptive-qualitative approach was employed, using thematic analysis to achieve the research objectives. This method allowed for an in-depth exploration of the narrative experiences of the participants and produced comprehensive, detailed findings.

4.1. Summary of Findings—The study revealed that school coordinators were deeply involved in implementing the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) and shared a wide range of narrative experiences, coping with the challenges, and gained valuable insights into educational management, particularly in the areas of collaboration, effective communication, and the importance of holistic support for the well-being of the students. The following summarizes the key findings:

1. The study revealed that school coordinators and teachers involved in the SBFP shared diverse narrative experiences. Many expressed a strong commitment to improving student health and attendance, describing their roles as both rewarding and demanding. Teachers recounted the positive impact of the program on malnourished students, noting increased energy and enhanced classroom participation. However, they also highlighted the added administrative tasks and time constraints they faced while implementing the initiative.

2. The study revealed that, regarding the challenges encountered, participants identified issues such as limited resources, logistical setbacks, and occasional lack of parental involvement. Despite these obstacles, coordinators and teachers demonstrated adaptability by developing resourceful solutions, such as mobilizing

community support and optimizing available supplies. Their coping strategies often included teamwork, open communication, and creative problem-solving, which enabled them to navigate difficulties and maintain the effectiveness of the program.

3. The study further found that educational management insights gained from their involvement in the SBFP emphasized the importance of collaboration, flexibility, and community engagement. Teachers and coordinators recognized that successful program implementation relies on the collective efforts of the school, parents, and local partners. Their experiences fostered greater empathy and understanding of students' needs, as well as a renewed appreciation for the role of school-based nutrition programs in supporting holistic student development.

4.2. Conclusions—This study provides important implications for teachers, school leaders, policymakers, and other stakeholders in implementing the SBFP in schools. The findings highlighted the importance of SBFP in supporting student nutrition, and they imply that it positively affects the well-being of the learners.

1. The findings imply unique narrative perspectives and experiences of school coordinators actively involved in the SBFP for intermediate learners. These coordinators play a pivotal role in ensuring the program runs smoothly,

from overseeing food distribution to fostering collaboration among partners and prioritizing the health of the learners. Their stories reflect both the achievements and the challenges faced, providing an in-depth understanding of how the program operates at the ground level. Through active participation, it serves as the bridge between administrative goals and the real-life execution of the program.

2. The challenges of school coordinators have shown notable resourcefulness in addressing the difficulties that come with running the SBFP. The encounter constraints, such as limited supplies or logistical barriers, yet respond by building strong community ties, making the most of what is available, and adopting a positive mindset. The proactive approach, willingness to collaborate, and commitment to problem-solving have allowed them to keep the program effective and resilient even under pressure. These strategies underline the importance of community involvement and ongoing support for program sustainability.

3. The study points to the necessity of continuous cooperation, professional development, and sufficient resources for the SBFP's ongoing success. The experiences shared by school coordinators highlight the need for strong engagement from all stakeholders and robust policy backing to further enhance the program's outcomes. Beyond its nutritional benefits, the SBFP contributes to better student attendance, improved focus in class, and stronger ties between schools and the wider community.

Furthermore, drawing from Bandura's Social Learning Theory and Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, the research affirms that meeting students' basic needs is essential for their motivation and learning. Ultimately, the study suggests integrating nutrition with social and behavioral support to promote overall growth and academic achievement among students.

4.3. *Recommendations*—Based on the findings and implications of the study, several

recommendations underscore the need for the intended audience to communicate and implement the results effectively. The SBFF at the intermediate level should focus on enhancing sustainability and community involvement. Integrating local resources and encouraging parent participation can strengthen program impact and foster a sense of ownership among stakeholders. Additionally, leveraging technology for monitoring and feedback will improve program efficiency and responsiveness.

1. School Coordinators, Local Government Officials, and Community Leaders. Strengthening partnerships among these stakeholders is essential to securing resources, fostering a sense of ownership, and expanding the program's reach. Active collaboration will facilitate resource mobilization, policy support, and community engagement, all of which are vital to the program's long-term viability. By working together, these groups can address challenges more effectively and create a supportive environment that ensures the program's continued success for intermediate students.

2. Teachers and School Health Personnel. Leverage technology to monitor students' progress, collect feedback, and evaluate program effectiveness. Digital tools enable real-time tracking and data collection, allowing for timely adjustments and personalized interventions. This integration of technology enhances the overall efficiency of the SBFF and ensures it remains responsive to evolving nutritional and health needs of the learners. As a result, program delivery becomes more targeted, impactful, and sustainable, ultimately improving student well-being and academic performance.

3. The Department of Education (DepEd). The role of DepEd should be to develop policies that support the integration and sustainability of SBFF in schools nationwide. They can also facilitate training for school staff and coordinate resources for program expansion.

4. Future Researchers are encouraged to ex-

plore strategies that strengthen the sustainability of the SBFP at the intermediate level, particularly by fostering greater community involvement. It is recommended that future studies examine effective ways to engage stakeholders and ensure the long-term impact of the program.

5. References

- ADB Annual Report 2023. (2024). Asian development bank [ADB Annual Report 2023. (2024, April 25). Asian Development Bank. <https://www.adb.org/documents/adbannual-report-2023>]. <https://www.adb.org/documents/adbannual-report-2023>
- Alcantara, A., & Fronteras, M. (2024). School-based feeding programs and academic performance: A quasi-experimental study on elementary learners [Alcantara, A., & Fronteras, M. (2024). School-based feeding programs and academic performance: A quasi-experimental study on elementary learners. *Journal of Educational Research*, 12(1), 45-59.].
- Assefa, E. A. (2026). From nutrition to education: The contributions of school feeding programs on the un 2030 agenda and au 2063 goals british food journal [Assefa, E. A. (2026). From nutrition to education: the contributions of school feeding programs on the UN 2030 Agenda and AU 2063 goals *British Food Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-03-2025-0311>]. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-03-2025-0311>
- Assefa, Y., Abebaw, D., & Berhanu, G. (2020). Impact of school-based feeding programs on educational outcomes in sub-saharan africa: A review of evidence [Assefa, Y., Abebaw, D., & Berhanu, G. (2020). Impact of school-based feeding programs on educational outcomes in sub-Saharan Africa: A review of evidence. *African Journal of Public Health*.].
- Backhaus, I., Varela, A. R., Khoo, S., Siefken, K., Crozier, A., Begotaraj, E., Fischer, F., Wiehn, J., Lanning, B., Lin, P., Jan, S., Zaranza Monteiro, L., Al-Shamli, A., La Torre, G., & Kawachi, I. (2020). Associations between social capital and depressive symptoms among college students in 12 countries: Results of a cross-national study [Backhaus, I., Varela, A. R., Khoo, S., Siefken, K., Crozier, A., Begotaraj, E., Fischer, F., Wiehn, J., Lanning, B., Lin, P., Jan, S., Zaranza Monteiro, L., Al-Shamli, A., La Torre, G., & Kawachi, I. (2020). Associations between social capital and depressive symptoms among college students in 12 countries: Results of a cross-national study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00644>]. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00644>
- Balansag, J. (2025). "from hunger to hope: The best practices of sbfp in an iped school," international journal of research and innovation in applied science, international journal of research and innovation in applied science (ijrias), vol [Balansag, J. (2025). "From Hunger to Hope: The Best Practices of SBFP in an IPED School," *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Applied Science*, *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Applied Science (IJRIAS)*, vol. 10(3)].
- Bilbar, A. (2020a). Effectiveness of school's feeding program in coping pupils' malnutrition on their academic performance [Bilbar, A. (2020). Effectiveness of School's Feeding Program in Coping Pupils' Malnutrition on Their Academic Performance. *IJRDO-Journal of Educational Research*, 5(5), 110-124.].
- Bilbar, A. (2020b). Effectiveness of school's feeding program in coping pupils' malnutrition on their academic performance [Bilbar, A. (2020). Effectiveness of School's Feeding Program in Coping Pupils' Malnutrition on Their Academic Performance. *IJRDO-Journal of Educational Research*, 5(5), 110-124. <https://doi.org/10.53555/er.v5i5.3707>]. <https://doi.org/10.53555/er.v5i5.3707>]
- Candelanza, Jane & Comighud, Sheena Mae. (2020). Looking at the perceived benefits of feeding program in the eyes of the stakeholders [Candelanza, Jane & Comighud, Sheena Mae. (2020). Looking at the Perceived Benefits of Feeding Program in the Eyes of the Stakeholders. 6. 1-25. [10.5281/zenodo.3865895](https://zenodo.org/record/3865895)].
- Chabrol, V. (2023). ,5 suggestions to ensure school feeding programs are sustainable; sustainable;<https://www.globalpartnership.org/ensure-school-feeding-programs-are-sustainable>; <https://www.globalpartnership.org/ensure-school-feeding-programs-are-sustainable>]. <https://www.globalpartnership.org/ensure-school-feeding-programs-are-sustainable>
- Claros, J.M., Cruz, Y., & Bacang, A.G. (2024a). The roles of teachers' knowledge and implementation of school-based feeding program on pupils' academic performance [Claros, J.M., Cruz, Y., & Bacang, A.G. (2024). The roles of teachers' knowledge and implementation of school-based feeding program on pupils' academic performance. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 2(7), 164-172. <https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2024.0142>]. <https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2024.0142>
- Claros, J.M., Cruz, Y., & Bacang, A.G. (2024b). The roles of teachers' knowledge and implementation of school-based feeding program on pupils' academic performance [Claros, J.M., Cruz, Y., & Bacang, A.G. (2024). The roles of teachers' knowledge and implementation of school-based feeding program on pupils' academic performance. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 2(7), 164-172. <https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2024.0142>]. <https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2024.0142>
- Cope, D. G. (2022). Ensuring research integrity in qualitative studies [Cope, D. G. (2022). Ensuring research integrity in qualitative studies. *Nursing Research Review*, 72(1), 12–20. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NNR.0000000000000581>]. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NNR.0000000000000581>
- Corpuz, S. G., & Bantulo, J. S. (2023). Level of effectiveness, sustainability of school-basedfeeding program, nutritional status, and academic performance of pupils amidst covid-19 pandemic: Basis for a proposed project busog talino program [Corpuz, S. G., & Bantulo, J. S. (2023). Level of effectiveness, sustainability of school-basedfeeding program, nutritional status, and academic performance of pupils amidst covid-19 pandemic: basis for a proposed project busog talino program. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 10(7). <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v10i7.4880>]. <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v10i7.4880>
- Cruz, M. L. A., Santos, J. R. G., & Reyes, C. L. (2020). Impact evaluation of the school-based feeding program in the philippines: A community-engaged approach [Cruz, M. L. A., Santos, J. R. G., & Reyes, C. L. (2020). Impact evaluation of the school-based feeding program in the Philippines: A community-engaged approach. *Journal of Community Engagement and Sustainable Development*.].

- Dacal, R., et al. (2020). Implementation of school-based feeding program and its effect on the physical growth and academic performance [Dacal, R., et al (2020). Implementation of School-Based Feeding Program and Its Effect on the Physical Growth and Academic Performance. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, Volume 3, No. 2, ISSN 2651-6691].
- De Mesa JAC, Gutierrez NMD, Romandi JMPM, Valencia NCC. (2023). Food accessibility of sitio san roque during the covid-19 pandemic [De Mesa JAC, Gutierrez NMD, Romandi JMPM, Valencia NCC (2023). Food accessibility of Sitio San Roque during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Cosmos J Eng Technol*. 2023. Jan-Jun;13(1):33–50. doi: 10.46360/cosmos.et.620231004.]. <https://doi.org/10.46360/cosmos.et.620231004>
- Demerin, M. G. L. (2023). Effect of school-based feeding program implementation of elementary schools on learners' academic performance [Demerin, M. G. L. (2023). Effect of school-based feeding program implementation of elementary schools on learners' academic performance. *International Journal of Research and Publications*, 120(1), 27-36. <https://doi.org/10.47119/IJRP1001201320234484>].
- Deuna , G. and Doncillo, O. (2024). Practices of elementary schools on the implementation of school-based feeding program from pre-pandemic to post-pandemic [Deuna , G. and Doncillo, O. (2024). Practices of Elementary Schools on the Implementation of School-Based Feeding Program from Pre-Pandemic to Post-Pandemic.].
- Dopmeijer, J. M. (2021). Running on empty [Dopmeijer, J. M. (2021). Running on empty. The impact of challenging student life on wellbeing and academic performance. Doctoral dissertation, University of Amsterdam]. Digital Academic Repository].
- Dukhi, N. (2020a). The impact of malnutrition on cognitive development and academic performance in children [Dukhi, N. (2020). The impact of malnutrition on cognitive development and academic performance in children. *South Eastern European Journal of Public Health*.].
- Dukhi, N. (2020b). The impact of malnutrition on cognitive development and academic performance in children [Dukhi, N. (2020). The impact of malnutrition on cognitive development and academic performance in children. *South Eastern European Journal of Public Health*, 4(2), 19-28.].
- Eryilmaz, Ö. (2022). Are dissertations trustworthy enough? the case of turkish ph [Eryilmaz, Ö. (2022). Are dissertations trustworthy enough? The case of Turkish ph. d. dissertations on social studies education. *Participatory Educational Research*, 9(3), 344-361.].
- Flores, K. C. (2023). Parental involvement in school-based feeding programs [Flores, K. C. (2023). Parental involvement in school-based feeding programs. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 12(7). <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2023.54>]. <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2023.54>
- Ganeshu, P., Fernando, T., & Keraminiyage, K. (2023). Barriers to, and enablers for, stakeholder collaboration in risk-sensitive urban planning: A systematised literature review [Ganeshu, P., Fernando, T., & Keraminiyage, K. (2023). Barriers to, and Enablers for, Stakeholder Collaboration in Risk-Sensitive Urban Planning: A Systematised Literature Review. *Sustainability*.].
- Gentles, S. J., Charles, C., Ploeg, J., & McKibbin, K. A. (2021). Sampling in qualitative research: Insights from a meta-study [Gentles, S. J., Charles, C., Ploeg, J., & McKibbin, K. A. (2021). Sampling in qualitative research: Insights from a meta-study. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 20, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069211004276>]. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069211004276>
- Gitau, P. W., Abayo, R., & Kibuine, M. (2020). Influence of organizational resource allocation and strategy communication on organizational performance of selected supermarkets in nairobi county [Gitau, P. W., Abayo, R., & Kibuine, M. (2020). Influence of organizational resource allocation and strategy communication on organizational performance of selected supermarkets in Nairobi County. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*.].
- Hablero, J. M. (2018). Benefits of school-based feeding program [Hablero, J. M. (2018, February 4). Benefits of School-Based Feeding Program. *PressReader.com - Digital Newspaper & Magazine Subscriptions*.].
- Hawthorne, H. (2023). What is adaptive teaching? <https://doi.org/https://www.highspeedtraining.co.uk/hub/what-is-adaptive-teaching>
- Herrity, J. (2025). 12 benefits of effective time management; <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/benefits-of-time-management> [Herrity, J. (2025), 12 Benefits of Effective Time Management; <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/benefits-of-time-management>]. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/benefits-of-time-management>
- Hunter, M. C., Sheaffer, C. C., Culman, S. W., & Jungers, J. M. (2020). Effects of defoliation and row spacing on intermediate wheatgrass i: Grain production [Hunter, M. C., Sheaffer, C. C., Culman, S. W., & Jungers, J. M. (2020). Effects of defoliation and row spacing on intermediate wheatgrass I: Grain production. *Agronomy Journal*, <https://doi.org/10.1002/agj2>. 20128]. <https://doi.org/10.1002/agj2>
- Jones, C. (2020). Do not forget the parents: Preparing trainee teachers for family–school partnership. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/25783858>
- Jones, C. D., & Lee, M. (2021). Teachers' perception of student learning needs: Implications for instructional practice [Jones, C. D., & Lee, M. (2021). Teachers' perception of student learning needs: Implications for instructional practice. *Journal of Educational Research*, 115(4), 489-503. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2021.1961859>]. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2021.1961859>
- Kopyto, H. (2025). , optimise your work and your life with effective time management [Kopyto, H. (2025), Optimise your work and your life with effective time management].
- Kosche, C., Rolader, R., and Yeung, H. (2021). , respect for human subjects: Ethics in research design; doi:10.1007/978-3-030-56861-0_41dermatoethics, contemporary ethics and professionalism in dermatology [Kosche, C., Rolader, R., and Yeung, H. (2021), Respect for Human Subjects: Ethics in Research Design; DOI:10.1007/978-3-030-56861-0_41Dermatoethics, Contemporary Ethics and Professionalism in Dermatology.]. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-56861-0_41Dermatoethics
- Kristjansson, E. (2022). , school feeding programs for improving the physical and psychological health of school children experiencing socio-economic disadvantage [Kristjansson, E. (2022), School feeding programs for improving the physical and psychological health of school children experiencing socio-economic disadvantage. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014794>].

- Kujala, J., Sachs, S., Leinonen, H., Heikkinen, A. & Laude, D. (2022). Stakeholder engagement: Past, present, and future [Kujala, J., Sachs, S., Leinonen, H., Heikkinen, A. & Laude, D. (2022). Stakeholder engagement: Past, present, and future. *Business & Society*, 61(5), 1136-1196. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00076503211066595>. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00076503211066595>]
- Lacanilao, R. (2020). Stakeholders' participation in school activities in public secondary schools in los baños, laguna [Lacanilao, R. (2020). Stakeholders' Participation in School Activities in Public Secondary Schools in Los Baños, Laguna. *Asian Journal of Social Science and Management Studies*. Vol 7.]
- Lang, L., et al. (2019). Nutrition interventions in schools: A review of evidence-based practices for improving student health outcomes [Lang, L., et al. (2019). Nutrition interventions in schools: A review of evidence-based practices for improving student health outcomes. *Journal of School Health*, 89(4), 280-290.]
- Lara, L., & Saracostti, M. (2019). Effect of parental involvement on children's academic achievement in Chile. *frontiers in psychology* [Lara, L., & Saracostti, M. (2019). Effect of parental involvement on children's academic achievement in Chile. *Frontiers in Psychology*].
- MatiMartinez, L., Nguyen, T., & Patel, R. (2020). Optimizing food preparation and distribution in school-based feeding programs: A case study analysis [MatiMartinez, L., Nguyen, T., & Patel, R. (2020). Optimizing Food Preparation and Distribution in School-Based Feeding Programs: A Case Study Analysis. *Journal of School Health*, 50(3), 210-225. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josh.12876>]
- Mojica-Sevilla, F., & Mark Hanzel. (2023). Philippine department of education's school-based feeding program [Mojica-Sevilla, F., & Mark Hanzel. (2023). Philippine Department of Education's School-Based Feeding Program.]
- Ortiz, K., Nash, J., Shea, L., Oetzel, J., Garoutte, J., Sanchez-Youngman, S., & OaksMorata, S. (2023). , implementation of school-based feeding program among the elementary schools in the school division of quezon: Basis for amendments on the sbfp operational guidelines [Ortiz, K., Nash, J., Shea, L., Oetzel, J., Garoutte, J., Sanchez-Youngman, S., & OaksMorata, S. (2023). Implementation of School-Based Feeding Program Among the Elementary Schools in the School Division of Quezon: Basis for Amendments on the SBFP Operational Guidelines.]
- Pecorari, D. (2021). Academic integrity in research writing [Pecorari, D. (2021). Academic integrity in research writing. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 50, 100972. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2021.100972>. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2021.100972>]
- Pérez-Escamilla, R., & Engmann, C. (2019). Integrating nutrition services into health care systems platforms: Where are we and where do we go from here [Pérez-Escamilla, R., & Engmann, C. (2019). Integrating nutrition services into health care systems platforms: Where are we and where do we go from here. *Maternal & child nutrition*, 15 Suppl 1(Suppl 1), e12743. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mcn.12743>. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mcn.12743>]
- Rahmah, H. A., Anggraini, A., Nilasari, Y. P., & Salsabilla, E. P. (2025). Integrative perspectives of social and science journal, 2(2 mei), 2855–2866 [Rahmah, H. A., Anggraini, A., Nilasari, Y. P., & Salsabilla, E. P. (2025). Integrative Perspectives of Social and Science Journal, 2(2 Mei), 2855–2866.]
- Reyes, Anthony Ian H. (2025). , deped expands school-based feeding program to combat malnutrition; <https://pia.gov.ph/news/deped-expands-school-based-feeding-program-to-combat-malnutrition>; [Reyes, Anthony Ian H. (2025), DepEd expands school-based feeding program to combat malnutrition; <https://pia.gov.ph/news/deped-expands-school-based-feeding-program-to-combat-malnutrition>. <https://pia.gov.ph/news/deped-expands-school-based-feeding-program-to-combat-malnutrition>]
- Robertson, T. (2021). Nutrition education in schools supports health [Robertson, T. (2021, October 4). Nutrition Education in Schools Supports Health. Retrieved from <https://www.healthyeating.org/blog/detail/nutrition-education-in-schools-supportshealth>]. <https://www.healthyeating.org/blog/detail/nutrition-education-in-schools-supportshealth>]
- Rodriguez, L., & Patel, R. (2020). Assessment of financial management practices in school-based feeding programs: A case study approach [Rodriguez, L., & Patel, R. (2020). Assessment of Financial Management Practices in School-Based Feeding Programs: A Case Study Approach. *Journal of School Health*.]
- Sahagun, J. A. (2022). Operational practices of school program: An evaluation to the implementation of school-based feeding program [Sahagun, J. A. (2022). Operational Practices of School Program: An Evaluation to the implementation of School-Based Feeding Program. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation*, 1(1), 24–28.]
- Silva, A. de A., Gubert, F., Barbosa Filho, V. B., Freitas, R., Vieira-Meyer, A., Pinheiro, M. M., & Rebouças, L. (2021). Health promotion actions in the school health program [Silva, A. de A., Gubert, F., Barbosa Filho, V. B., Freitas, R., Vieira-Meyer, A., Pinheiro, M. M., & Rebouças, L. (2021). Health promotion actions in the School Health Program.]
- Smith, C., Goss, H. R., Issartel, J., & Belton, S. (2021). Health literacy in schools? a systematic review of health-related interventions aimed at disadvantaged adolescents [Smith, C., Goss, H. R., Issartel, J., & Belton, S. (2021). Health Literacy in Schools? A Systematic Review of Health-Related Interventions Aimed at Disadvantaged Adolescents.]
- Solania, N. L., & Cubillas, A. U. (2020). Implementation of the school-based feeding program of public elementary schools: Basis for teachers' capacity enhancement training [Solania, N. L., & Cubillas, A. U. (2020). Implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program of Public Elementary Schools: Basis for Teachers' Capacity Enhancement Training. *International Journal of English and Education* ISSN, 2278-4012.]
- Tatad, E.F. (2025). Nourishing minds: An exploration of school-basedfeedingprogram management practices in bansalan east district; doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15869719> [Tatad, E.F., (2025), Nourishing Minds: An Exploration of School-BasedFeedingProgram Management Practices in Bansalan East District; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15869719>]. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15869719>]
- Viajar, R. V., Dorado, J. B., Azaña, G. P., Ibarra, H. A., Ferrer, E. B., & Capanzana, M. V. (2020). Process evaluation of nutrition intervention strategy in a local philippine setting. *journal of primary care & community health* [Viajar, R. V., Dorado, J. B., Azaña, G. P., Ibarra, H. A., Ferrer, E. B., & Capanzana, M. V. (2020). Process evaluation of nutrition intervention strategy in a local Philippine setting. *Journal of Primary Care & Community Health*.]

- Vizcocho, D. J. D. (2022). Problems encountered by school-based feeding program beneficiaries and their academic performance [Vizcocho, D. J. D. (2022a). Problems Encountered by School-Based Feeding Program Beneficiaries and Their Academic Performance.].
- Wabe, M.E.L., Pontillas, P. & Comon, J. (2024). ; practices and challenges of school-based feeding program of opol west district; european modern studies journal 8(4):278-318; doi:10.59573 [Wabe, M.E.L., Pontillas, P. & Comon, J. (2024); Practices and Challenges of School-Based Feeding Program of Opol West District; European Modern Studies Journal 8(4):278-318; DOI:10.59573.]. <https://doi.org/10.59573>
- Webb, P., Kennedy, C., & Kuroda, T. (2018). The impact of nutrition interventions on academic performance: A global overview [Webb, P., Kennedy, C., & Kuroda, T. (2018). The impact of nutrition interventions on academic performance: A global overview. Global Health Action, 11(1), 1-13.].
- WFP. (2020). State of school feeding worldwide 2020 [WFP (2020). State of School Feeding Worldwide 2020. Rome, World Food Programme].
- WFP School Feeding Infographic. (2020). World food programme [WFP School Feeding Infographic (2020) World Food Programme.].
- World Health Organization: WHO. (2024). , malnutrition [World Health Organization: WHO. (2024a), Malnutrition].
- Zerga, E., et al. (2022). Nutritional disparities in school-age children [Zerga, E., et al. (2022). Nutritional disparities in school-age children. Global Health Journal, 14(1), 56-65.].
- Zoloth, S. (2023). , time management: What is it and why is it important? [Zoloth, S. (2023), Time Management: What Is It and Why Is It Important?].